

ENGLISH CURRICULUM RENEWAL IN SCHOOLS

*F. Nuriddinova*¹, *Z. Nuriddinova*², *G. Yuldasheva*³

Abstract:

Curriculum is to have been formulated by the history, psychological and philosophical minds, educational theorists and scholars of the society. Curriculum is viewed the planned chain of the content sequence of a grade-cohort subject. Curriculum is the sequel of one`s life experience and should also be the others`. "Social and political developments are the factors for the curriculum implementation or vice versa" (Bobbit, 1918). As long as the huge percentage of the world population are the client of education curriculum and its inclusions necessarily shape the mindsets of them with sticking to curricular products. Technological changes remind individuals what have been transformed and what should consecutively be, also, how we need to educate. Information technology and communication have been the answer how recent curricula of advanced educational systems possess all needed multi-dimensional inclusions of educational requirements. "The present-day technology advances in curricula development are becoming more and more varied with the reforms of government authorities, school analytic experts, scholars of educational managements, all of which are essential assets of curriculum recourse" (Korn., 2004). As technological breakthroughs roar, "massive updates began filling the gaps of should-be definitions of curriculum" (Bronkhorst., 2000). New technological instructions regulate the challenges of school learners and these are by far the fastest mobilizing and changing aspects of the world. Technology-blended curriculum matches the uncertain world of the future with its electronic, computerized and verbiage features. Up-to-now curriculum is structured concerning the age-cohort because of which is significantly suggested that knowledge acquisition varies among ages. However, there still remain gaps in comprehending stratification, likely regarding the gender.

Key words: curricula development, computerized and verbiage features, up-to-now curriculum, philosophical resources, consequent vision, educational breakthrough, underpinning resources.

Introduction

Key effective factor to change is fostering new innovations in the edges of the former situation (Brown and Eisenhardt, 1998).

The present-day curriculum of Uzbekistan is the consequent vision of the mistakes and achievements of the past (from the dawn of Educational Revolution in Central Asia to the scope of colonialism) and the next updates of the Curriculum should be inclusive of the continuation of the achievement sequence and eradication of the mistakes. The past is the great teacher that individuals can ever learn from, hence, there stand comparative breakthroughs of structuring educational curriculum based upon the most developed ones ahead of the education-managing scholars. Countless case studies, a plethora of philosophical resources of running educational institutions are supposed to be the underpinning resources on the purpose of responding this task.

History of Preschool Education

Tracking unofficial preschool education is controversial since the information resources of Preschool in up-to-colonization of Central Asia.

The preschool curriculum in Soviet Union was almost "the same educational documentation and the same way of teaching" (Brickman, 1964; Fitzpatrick, 1971). The second implementation was that "few changes in preschool education and no authority to school directors to employ something new" (Aliyev, 1984). "The only changes occurred in the preschool reformation had been reformed by Stalin and Brezhnev era" (Tudge, 1973).

History of Primary Education

¹ *Nuriddinova Fotima Quqhor kizi, Teacher at the department of "General science", Narpay Foreign Language Faculty, Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages*

² *Nuriddinova Zukhra Quqhor kizi, Teacher at the department of "General science", Narpay Foreign Language Faculty, Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages*

³ *Yuldasheva Gulsara Bakhriddinovna, Teacher of the Pharmacology Department, Samarkand State University of Medicine*

As the central topic of this unit, the history of primary education of Uzbekistan was unfairly unsubstantial. 20% children of Soviet Central Asia had the political and financial chance to attend the primary school, “the percentages of literacy varied from 2%-8%” (Kuzin, 1977). Coming to the 1930s, after the Red Revolution, the Ministry of Enlightenment launched “projects (complexes), the ways to the formal didactic system of teaching elementary school children that still are noticed in current schooling of post-Soviet countries” (Brickman, 1964; Fitzpatrick, 1971).

After the split of Soviet Union, the factor that would influence the educational development was the long-term concern of refining the outdated remains of the former Empire. Most of the Eastern Europe countries, for example, underwent educational practices in a passive medium.

The diagram explains the amount of changes in post-Soviet East Asian Countries Curricula in percentage values, based on the statistic features in Heyneman, Stephen P.: Educational Choices in Eastern Europe and the former Soviet Union - Review Essay - Educational Economics (Volume 5, No.3, 2019) pp.333-339.

The changes referred in the diagram pointed out the transformation in implementing new world educational agendas into curricula. One of those global educational agendas was the extension of English across the Eastern World.

The acceptance of English in post-Soviet Uzbekistan correlated the volume of willingness of other Central Asian countries, according to the facts of Richard, J. C., (2021).

This novel branch, initially, filled the secondary and higher educational systems with new curricula extras. Nevertheless, as the language of scientific research and global media, English needed to be polished through extra curricular activities in the curriculum system of primary education, which defined the increase in the acceptance of this subject.

Those charts depict the changes in the primary education curriculum of Uzbekistan because of the subjects additional of the new world and English in the scope of hours in a week, in 1989, 2009 and the period up until the present day, respectively.

History of Secondary Education

However so difficult to be isolated from the stable 70 years, said Vasilieva (1992), academic subject areas above elementary level, have been chosen on the basis of their importance as they become foundations on outward looking, free-market oriented, democratic and civil societies. “At the centre such subjects as sociology, politics, humanism and foreign languages, the latter education system of secondary level aimed at catching up with the internal functioning of democratic government” (Kuhn., 2005).

History of Higher Education

Asilov, B. (2005) described that the introduction of higher education level programs for English academic study (2015) helped to lay foundations for the emergence of English experts in teaching education (pedagogical institutes) that would control the attempts to spread English-specific academic areas to the lower layers (secondary and primary education). This idea was to complete the change in excluding a number of outdated subject areas and embodying the development-relevant subjects in democratic country.

Conclusion

The standards and norms of the field of Education - UNESCO - of the UN suggest that Language Curriculum Development should answer the following questions:

1. “Educational values and principles should be used to determine the content of a curricular language program?”
2. Contextual factors are needed to be into account in planning language teaching syllabus?
3. The aims and objectives of teaching, are concerning to serve one`s (pupil`s) interests?
4. Local/global issues are supposed to be selected, adopted in designing instructional materials for the course units?

See also Cummins, J. and Davison, C. (2007) The global scope and policies of ELT: Critiquing current policies and programmes. In J. Cummins and C. Davison (Eds), International handbook of English language teaching (Vol. 1, pp. 237–248). New York: Springer.

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